

Existential Humanism: Processing the Fragility of Life

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[This is a transcript prepared for an informal talk, not an academic article.]

In 2009 I produced a collection of twelve essays about Ethical Culture – a non-theist, humanist congregational movement which is 140 years old – as part of my preparation to for a new career in Ethical Culture clergy. It started with these words:

I begin with choice. It is uniquely mine. I cannot avoid it. Even if I don't choose, that is a choice. And, I have no choice but to take responsibility for my choices. I make these choices in profound ignorance, during a very short existence. This is what I call the existential perspective on life. I have it.

When I tell people that I'm an existentialist I get different responses - suspicion, interest, pity, blank stares. Existentialism also involves a profound embrace of limitation and a deep awareness of our mortality. Over recent years as climate change and pandemic heighten my sense of limitation and mortality, my existentialism is reawakened. It is reawakened because mankind is destroying the delicate biosphere that keeps us alive and the pandemic has accentuated our limitations.

Existentialism, however, has helped me process not only my limitations, but it helps me build meaning in my life. But before I begin, a couple of caveats: First, this is not a formal philosophical talk with a clear, linear argument. It's more of a collection of thoughts. Second, I'm not trying to explain all existential perspective, just mine.

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As young person, I liked laughing at death. I still like dark humor. I realize, of course, that mortality is deadly serious. I think we need to do more than laugh at it. We need to wrestle with it in a way to accentuate the importance of life. Existential philosopher Albert Camus said, "There is but one truly serious philosophical problem, and that is suicide. Judging whether life is or is not worth living amounts to answering the fundamental question of philosophy." One's answer can have profound consequences.

Existentialists are acutely aware of their mortality. They're conscious that they will not always be - that their unique experience will end. Soren Kierkegaard, called by some the "first existentialist," viewed facing death as the fundamental human challenge. It's the ultimate "leveling" reality in life. Our existence will disappear in the eternity that stretches on after we die.

In the stories of existentialist Jean Paul Sartre, characters contemplate their own non-existence. Sartre portrays this experience as universal - death is an immovable barrier, a darkness that both attracts us and denies us. We can't enter into it, but it frames our life.

In Sartre's story *The Wall*, Juan Mirbal is condemned to die by firing squad. As he contemplates his execution, he imagines the wall that will soon be at his back before he is shot. He tries to imagine entering into the wall and going beyond it, but he cannot.

He laments his fate: "Someone'll holler 'aim!' and I'll see eight rifles looking at me. I'll think how I'd like to get inside the wall, I'll push against it with my back...with every ounce of strength I have, but the wall will stay, like in a nightmare. I can imagine all that. If you only knew how well I can imagine it." (Kaufmann 289)

Simone de Beauvoir, the writer who put up with Sartre's brooding during their life-long relationship as a couple, perhaps had a healthier attitude about death. She writes, "It is useless to try to integrate life and death and to behave rationally in the presence of something that is not rational: each must manage as well as he can in the tumult of his feelings." In *The Ethics of Ambiguity* she adds, "Today...we are having a hard time living because we are so bent on outwitting death."

For me, being honest about death includes putting a period at the end of the last sentence of my life. It's the end of the story. I agree with Unitarian Universalist minister Bill Murray who says, "For the religious humanist death is not evil, but it is final" (Murray, 95). This existential perspective colors my humanism - it humbles me, connects me with all other conscious mortal creatures, and asks me to live fully here and now. It infuses my philosophy of life.

During my years of teaching high school, I read much Howard Gardner, an educator who categorized forms of “intelligences” or ways of learning and processing information, including linguistic, mathematical, and kinesthetic. Currently he’s considering adding a category he calls “existential intelligence.” Those who score high in this area enjoy thinking and questioning. They’re curious about life, death, and ultimate realities.

Historical figures Gardner claims would score high in this intelligence include Aristotle, Confucius, Emerson, Einstein, and Plato. As Plato says, through the voice of Socrates, “Ordinary people seem not to realize that those who really apply themselves in the right way to philosophy are directly and of their own accord preparing themselves for dying and death.”

The founder of Ethical Culture, Felix Adler, in *The Essentials of Spirituality*, touches on how contemplating mortality clarifies our ethical perspective. He writes, “The frank facing of death...has the effect of sifting out the true values of life from the false, the things that are worthwhile from the things that are not worthwhile, the things that are related to the highest end and those related to the lower partial ends.” (p. 19) This is true for me. Existentialism helps me sort out my values: it’s made clearer my dedication to the worth of all individuals, the value of ethical relationships, and the importance of social justice.

So, let me descend further into existentialism by examining some of the vocabulary existentialists brooded about down at the café. Take the three “A’s”: Abandonment, Anguish, and Absurdity.

Sartre and other existentialists used the term **abandonment** to describe the modern human condition. For most it represented our condition of having been abandoned by God. The growing atheism of the 20th century - along with the horrors of war and alienation - convinced some that “god was dead” no more so than existentialist Nietzsche who blamed human consciousness and genius for this murder:

Whither is God. I shall tell you. We have killed him -- you and I. All of us are his murderers.... Do we not hear anything yet the noise of the grave-diggers who are burying God? Do we not smell anything yet of God's decomposition? Gods too decompose. God is dead. God remains dead. And we have killed him. (Kaufmann, p. 126)

All existentialists agree that abandonment means we no longer can be certain. *Certainty* has left us. Between our consciousness and all else is the chasm of doubt. We stand in solitude on the brink of a great abyss. We have to make the leap solo. We act without a guide. There are no excuses. In this way, we are alone.

The second “A” - **anguish** - arises when we appreciate that we must choose aware that we know nothing for certain. Sartre offers the biblical example of Abraham, ordered apparently by an angel of God to sacrifice his own son. On the surface the horror is that Abraham has two choices, neither very attractive: killing his son or disobeying God. A fanatic might escape this dilemma by rationalizing that, given the glory of eternal afterlife, the son will be better off in heaven + soon enough father and son will be reunited.

Abraham, more typical than fanatic, cannot so rationalize, so he suffers. Abraham cannot know for sure. Should the angel be real, and truly expressing God’s wishes, that would be one thing. In killing, he would be a noble soldier of God, steadfast in allegiance, sacrificing for a higher cause. For Abraham, the anguish in that case could be overcome by understanding - sadness over losing his son set in the context of a grand plan. This is unattractive enough.

But the true existential “anguish of Abraham” arises from the fact that Abraham does not know if the angel is real. What if it were the devil, or a hallucination? Then the sacrifice would be a sin before God and cause him to lose his precious son. Is the angel real? Is god real?

He has no way of being 100% sure; he alone must choose. Small in stature, limited in knowledge, he must decide what to believe and accept ultimate responsibility. The same is true for us with every decision we make. Even if we can consult a god, an expert, or a friend, it is ultimately up to us to decide when to ask, who to trust, and what to do.

This often leads us to the third “A” - **absurdity**. Abandoned to anguish alone and uncertain, we just don’t know when our intentions match reality. If Abraham thinks he’s killing his son for some divine purpose of an all-powerful god, but there is no such god or purpose, *intention clashes with reality*.

Camus offers a more concrete example: “(i)f I see a man armed only with a sword attack a group of machine guns, I shall consider his act to be absurd. But it is so solely by virtue of the disproportion between his intention and the reality he will

encounter, of the contradiction I notice between his true strength and the aim he has in view"(Gould, pp. 718-719). The disproportion between intention and reality is the absurd.

Others may say that "the absurd" is not as a clash of intention and reality, but simply the meaningless nature of reality itself. This singular fact means there's no necessity, no inherent reason for the way things are; reality could be arranged differently and it wouldn't matter.

As 17th century mathematician Blaise Pascal said: "When I consider the short duration of my life, swallowed up in the eternity before and after, the little space I fill, and even can see engulfed in the infinite immensity of space of which I am ignorant, and which knows me not, I am frightened, and am astonished at being here rather than there, why now rather than then." (Lavine, p. 331)

But in my experience, the world, in and of itself, is not absurd. The lack of objective meaning is not absurd. For me, the absurd arises in this clash of reality and intention: *the meaninglessness of reality and man's insistence on meaning*. In the words of Camus, "[i]t lies in neither of the elements compared; it is born of their confrontation." (Gould, p. 719.) Meaninglessness confronts our quest for meaning.

Camus insists, however, that the absurd does not point toward self-extinction. The absurd is not a threat to human life, but a creation of it. Only by living our life does the absurd live. The issue is not, according to Camus, whether the absurd should lead us to suicide, but rather that the absurd is possible only if we choose to live. He urges us to keep the absurd alive: *Living an experience, a particular fate, is accepting it fully. Now, no one will live this fate, knowing it to be absurd, unless he does everything to keep before him that absurd brought to light by consciousness. Negating one of the terms of the opposition on which he lives is to elude the problem. The theme of permanent revolution is thus carried into individual experience. Living is keeping the absurd alive.* (Sisyphus, p. 40)

Despite the lack of objective meaning in the world, the absurd provides us opportunity to create meaning. If one opts for suicide, the absurd is collapsed. Camus explains, *The absurd is born of this confrontation between the human need and the unreasonable silence of the world. In its way, suicide settles the absurd. It engulfs the absurd in the same death. But I know that in order to keep alive, the absurd cannot be settled. It escapes suicide to the extent that it is simultaneously awareness and rejection of death.... That revolt gives life its value. Spread out over the whole length of a life, it restores its majesty to that life. To a man devoid of blinders, there is no finer sight than that of the intelligence at grips with a reality that transcends it.*

TRANSCENDENCE THROUGH MEANING

There's no finer sight than that of intelligence at grips with a reality that transcends it - consciousness wrestling with what's beyond it - with a reality that will continue on without it, with the world on the other side of that wall. Heroes keep the absurd alive.

It is not always easy to keep the absurd alive. Psychotherapist Viktor Frankl, the seminal figure within "existential analysis," cared for many clients who saw life as meaningless and dark. Rather than offer them specific solutions, Frankl challenged clients to create their own meaning within their life as a whole - the good and the bad, the light and the dark.

Logotherapy, as Frankl called it, approaches life as a whole within which we are ultimately free to make many choices. We cannot deny circumstances of our life and our own animal nature - but we can choose how to respond to them. We cannot change the hand we have been dealt, but we can choose how to play the game.

The *Viktor Frankl Institut* mission declares, human freedom and responsibility challenges individuals "to bring forth the possible best in themselves and in the world, by perceiving and realizing the meaning of the moment in each and every situation." [<http://www.viktorfrankl.org/e/logotherapy.html>] It is a beautiful, creative, and invigorating challenge.

EXISTENTIAL LIMITS POSED BY CLIMATE CHANGE AND PANDEMICS

I need the energy I draw from Existentialism now more than ever. During this time of pandemic, there is disorientation and fear. This is layered on top of our growing awareness of the realities of climate change. My reactions to both the coronavirus and climate change are linked to an appreciation for the fragility of life.

Climate change might seem more remote than what we are going through now. But David Wallace-Wells, challenges that myth in his book, *The Uninhabitable Earth*. It's a scary book. It triggers anxiety in me similar to the anxiety caused by the pandemic. It awakens existential dread.

Wallace-Wells teaches us that things are moving fast. Half of carbon we have put in the atmosphere came during last three decades. We now have 10,000 people a day dying around the world from air pollution. One study estimates that in New Delhi, in 2017, simply breathing normally was as hazardous to your health as smoking 2 packs of cigarettes every day.

Many people are dying annually of hyperthermia. You may remember last summer's heat wave which set record temperatures in Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. Heat killed more than 500 in June and nearly 1000 in July. Back in 2010, 700 people a day were killed in Moscow for a grand total of 55,000!

Extreme heat triggers wildfires that come in greater intensity and frequency all over the world. The carbon released from tens of thousands of burnt acres increases the greenhouse effect already powered by 200 years of burning coal and a century of burning petroleum. As a result, melting polar ice leads to sea waters rising and violent storms, which, in 2017, flooded two-thirds of Bangladesh.

As the heat rises, more ice will melt, leaving the earth darker, thus absorbing more of the sun's rays, accelerating heating. From within arctic ice will soon be released diseases that have not circulated for millions of years, leaving us without built-up immunities to resist.

Heat causes "thousand-year storms" that devastate communities every couple of years, which strips the soil of nutrients 10 times more quickly than the nutrients are being replaced. Without sufficient fertile soil, food is becoming scarcer. Today 800 million people in the world are undernourished.

Changing weather patterns in East Africa generate locust clouds as big as cities, one estimated with 192 billion locusts. As temperate regions get hotter, mosquitos spread yellow fever and malaria moving northward from the tropics at about three miles every year. The World Bank estimates that by 2030, 3.6 billion people will be threatened by mosquito-borne diseases. Had enough of this yet?

DENIAL, DISORIENTATION, AND WITHDRAWAL

The unrelenting barrage in this book at first led me to downplay the dangers. Intellectually I don't reject the grim warnings by scientists, but sometimes I ask, "it couldn't be *that* bad, could it?"

Too many Americans, even U. S. environmental scientists, have been conditioned to downplay the threat. While scientific warnings are accepted more fully in Europe, in America the fossil fuel industry and their public relation firms call mainstream climatologists fatalistic and alarmist, and claim they're perpetrating a hoax. Their careers have been threatened. As a result, many have "erred on the side of complacency."

Perhaps we deny horrible environmental possibilities because of "psychic numbing," a term coined years ago by Jonathan Schell in his book *Fate of the Earth*. Schell was addressing the dangers of nuclear war, but the psychological adaptation he explains is similar. It's hard enough, Schell admits, to contemplate one's own death, and the deaths of loved ones. It was, he suggests, nearly impossible to imagine the demise of billions of humans or the end of all life. Trying to contemplate such extremes, Schell explains, leads to "psychic numbing that leaves us unable to act. We drift towards apathy, isolation, and indifference." Contemplating environmental collapse leads us to do the same. Theorist Timothy Morton calls the thought of environmental devastation a "hyperobject," a concept so large and complex that it can't be properly comprehended. The bigness of the problem leads us to avert our eyes.

Some accept the grim predictions and seek a different sort of withdrawal. In a section of his book entitled, "Ethics at the End of the World," Wallace-Wells speaks about Guy McPherson, a scientist who believes in "near-term human extinction." By the year 2030, McPherson estimates, the human race will be extinct. He is well aware such predictions are taken by the public as "linked to cults" or "something close to proof of insanity."

When environmentalists see the human race as a small and cancerous part of nature, some call it “inhumanism” and “anti-humanism.” They regard human beings as insignificant and not worth worrying about. Wallace-Wells explains that these positions are at best a stoic form of “reasonable detachment” and at worst a compassionless apathy. He criticizes this “retreat from politics...in the name of a slippery hedonistic quietism.”

Wallace-Wells goes deeper into other psychological dynamics that push us into denial or withdrawal. He writes of “anchoring,” which is our tendency to hold on to what seems stable, such as the day-to-day continuity of our relatively temperate world.

He explains the “ambiguity affect,” which uses any sense of uncertainty as a reason to do nothing. The “automation bias” is when we assume that “market forces” or “technology” will automatically save us. And there’s, of course, the “bystander affect,” a well-known tendency to remain passive and assume that others should act first.

But possibly the most seductive form of withdrawal I’ve encountered is a form “the loving witness” – acknowledging the accelerating deterioration of the biosphere but accepting it as inevitable. As Wallace-Wells writes, for such people, “[t]he meta-lesson is that we should draw roughly the same meaning from an understanding of the imminent death of the species as the Dalai Lama believes we should draw from an understanding of our imminent personal death – namely, compassion, wonderment, and above all, love.”

These are wonderful qualities, but our biosphere is *not* like a mortal creature like you and I, here for such a very temporary time. This thin layer of sea, soil, and sky that harbors all life that we know is *not* dying from inevitable causes. We’re destroying it.

Wallace-Wells says over and over again that the good news is that if we can change the biosphere so dramatically in two short centuries, that shows our human power. We need not succumb to “human futilitarianism.” We can resist. We can reclaim our power.

RECLAIMING OUR POWER

Reading *The Uninhabitable Earth* is a humbling experience. But it can, it should, it must, also be a call to action. Wallace-Wells counsels that having your eyes open should nurture “both human humility and human grandiosity, each drawn from the same perception of peril.” He insists that, while the biosphere is being rocked by our actions, its “instability is also a measure of the human power that engineered it.” He continues “If humans are responsible for the problem, they must be capable of undoing it.” Such an approach would help us in our present pandemic situation, wouldn’t it?

Regarding both this virus and threats to our fragile biosphere, we shouldn’t collapse in defeat, but we should redouble our efforts to promote sensible action. We need not fall back into romantic humanism. We need not be naïve about science being a magic wand.

We can take a more moderate path like the one suggested by James Lovelock, originator of the concept of Gaia, which portrays the earth as one remarkable, interrelated organism. He wrote, “Gaia, as I see her, is no doting mother tolerant of misdemeanors, nor is she some fragile and delicate damsel in danger from brutal mankind. She is stern and tough, always keeping the world warm and comfortable for those who obey the rules, but ruthless in her destruction of those who transgress.”

Now, I don’t endorse anthropomorphism – I don’t ascribe intent to nature. But *we have* transgressed! We will pay for our actions. How much we pay will depend on how well we use the tools at our disposal.

But there’s a lot we can do. We have tools at our disposal, which include using less, reusing, recycling, carbon tax, carbon capture, green energy, new types of agriculture, and less meat and dairy. Reviewer Jennifer Szalai compares *The Uninhabitable Earth* to *Silent Spring*, Rachel Carson’s rallying cry for the anti-toxins part of the Sixties environmental movement. Szalai suggests that Wallace-Well’s book could do for greenhouse gases what Carson’s 1962 book did for pesticides, becoming a “galvanizing force, a foundational text for the environmental movement.”

Our environmental crisis, as well as this pandemic, should have rightfully humbled us. We are not gods that hover above and control nature. As Wallace-Wells recently wrote about the dual threats to us, “Among the many unnerving lessons the two crises share is this one: Nature is mighty, and scary, and we have not defeated it but live within it, subject to its temperamental power, no matter where it is that you live or how protected you may normally feel.”

I’m scared by the coronavirus. I’m scared by climate change. And I should be. But it need not make me passive or lead me to withdraw and give up. Let us instead be fully present in this world. Chris Phillips, in a blog he calls “tiny Buddha,” wrote a piece titled, “Life Is Fragile,” in which he explains: “Facing up to the fragility of life can be scary. It can also be empowering. It can help us hold onto a perspective that supports us living a life rich with positive experiences. It can leave us with a conviction to make the most of our days.”

As we tend to Mother Earth, we are not helpless. We need not be reduced to being hospice nurses to a dying biosphere. We should work to protect and pass on to our children and their children the thin layer of life encircling the earth. We have the power to extend life beyond the life of the mortal creatures that currently live and breathe.

REKINDLING WONDER

Facing pandemic challenges and climate catastrophe, we may need some extra inspiration to reclaim our power. These threats disorient us, drain our energy, sometimes lead to retreat, withdrawal, surrender. During this coronavirus time, I have occasionally curled up on the couch in a fetal position. We might need some escape - to withdraw, to recharge.

But we need then to reengage with the world and be present. We need to thank the millions of health care and essential service workers braving public space every day to save our lives or just make them a bit better. We must try to help victims of classism, racism, and sexism how are more abused in times of crisis.

And, we must build on signs of greater solidarity in the world. In the last week or two I’ve read how our collective efforts might just be working. Last week, David Wallace-Wells said in the *Times* that he was blown away by our collective efforts to limit suffering and death. He wrote, “This is solidarity I simply didn’t believe was possible in this country anymore and under any circumstances, and it has arrived in the space of just weeks, in the midst of national political chaos with tribal partisanship still boiling at a feverish peak. It is breathtaking.”

We have a long way to go to make that solidarity real and lasting, especially for victims of systemic oppression. We need to be inspired by the ideal of this solidarity - this sense of connection with everyone on the surface of this planet if we are going to heal divisions, to repair the harm done to so many people without power. Perhaps only then will we have a better chance of nurturing the biosphere back to health.

With inspiration in mind, as I come close to the end of my talk, I invite you to take a deep breath. Imagine the earth from the perspective of outer space.

I find that the image of the earth from space helps me generate that sense of interconnectedness. The astronaut James Irwin said that when he saw our planet from a distance, it reminded him of a Christmas tree ornament, something that “looked so fragile, so delicate, that if you touched it with a finger it would crumble and fall apart.” For astronaut Rusty Schweikart, that beautiful fragility affected him profoundly. From his seat inside Apollo 9, he said, “You look down and you can’t imagine how many borders and boundaries you cross again and again and again. From where you see it, the earth is a whole...and it is so beautiful. There are no frames. There are no boundaries. When you go around the earth in an hour and a half you begin to recognize that your identity is with that whole thing. And that makes a change.”

The very science and technology that deluded us into thinking we were invincible, allowed Schweikart to feel profound humility looking back at earth. Soviet cosmonaut Sigmund Jahn said, “[b]efore I flew, I was already aware of how small and vulnerable our planet is, but only when I saw it from space, in all its ineffable beauty and fragility, did I realize that humankind’s most urgent task is to cherish and preserve it for future generations.” We inherited this amazing biosphere which sustains all life. We must protect it for the children and their children and their children down seven generations.

Ed Ericson, who was presented with a lifetime achievement award last year at our national assembly, spoke about this one Sunday half-century ago: “A generation never has the right to forfeit the future; it is not ours to hold hostage. . . . Not one of us is immortal. But we must safeguard with religious humility the immortality of the human future.” In honor of Earth

Day, acknowledging in this pandemic our remarkable interconnectedness, let us to see our oneness on planet earth and act accordingly. As Archibald MacLeish said, to “see the earth as we now see it, small and blue and beautiful in that eternal silence where it floats, is to see ourselves as riders on the earth together...” In all our fragility, we are one human family.

Thank you.